

Column Studies on Arsenic Removal from Ground Water for Filter Development in Rural Areas

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ABSTRACT

According to WHO, Arsenic is a natural component of the earth's crust and is widely distributed throughout the environment in the air, water and land. Arsenic is naturally present at high levels in the groundwater of several countries. It is highly toxic in its inorganic form. There are various methods of removal of arsenic from contaminated water like flocculation using iron coagulants or alum, iron oxide adsorption, activated alumina, ion exchange, electro dialysis reversal, nanotechnology based arsenic remediation etc. Since not all the techniques are economical so our experiment is solely based on the most available and cost effective method, the iron oxide adsorption method that includes the use of rusty nails in biosand filtration coated with iron oxide for eliminating As⁵⁺ from water samples through column tests. A series of column experiments were conducted using locally available materials. An iron oxide coated biosand filter showed the best arsenate removal efficiency, with up to 82% removal from column test studies. The adsorption rate tended to increase with the adsorbent dosage. Experiments at different iron oxide dosages confirmed that the adsorption of arsenate onto iron oxide particles followed a pseudo second-order model. The findings underscore the potential for developing cost-effective filtration systems that could be implemented in resource-limited settings to provide safe drinking water. Based on various column test studies, it can be concluded that a double filtration system is the most effective method for arsenic removal from groundwater. The first filter effectively removes arsenic, but during the process, it may increase iron concentrations due to contact with iron nails. However, the second filter is designed to remove both the excess iron and pathogens, ultimately producing treated water with reduced levels of both arsenic and iron. This two-step filtration process ensures more efficient removal of contaminants, providing cleaner and safer water. Also various physico-chemical parameters like turbidity, conductivity, hardness, alkalinity, chloride, fluoride, magnesium, calcium, nitrate tests are done to check this filter effectivity in these parameters removing.

Keywords: iron oxide, arsenic, iron, contamination, charcoal

INTRODUCTION

Groundwater is a vital source of drinking water in rural India, but its quality is severely compromised in many areas due to naturally occurring arsenic. Prolonged exposure to arsenic-contaminated water can lead to severe health issues such as skin lesions, internal cancers, and cardiovascular diseases. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) prescribe a maximum permissible limit of 0.01 mg/L for arsenic in drinking water, but in many rural areas, arsenic levels far exceed this guideline. Traditional treatment technologies are often economically and operationally unfeasible in rural settings. Despite awareness and ongoing remediation efforts, the challenge remains

largely unresolved in rural areas due to the lack of affordable, accessible, and low-maintenance water purification technologies. Most commercially available arsenic-removal systems are cost-prohibitive, require electricity or skilled operation, or involve maintenance complexities that are unsuitable for rural settings. The ultimate goal of this work is to contribute toward the development of a cost-effective, sustainable, and user-friendly household filtration system that rural communities can easily adopt using locally sourced materials—thereby enhancing access to safe drinking water and protecting public health.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Bretzler (2020) conducted an extensive investigation into zero-valent iron (ZVI) filters in Burkina Faso showed arsenic removal efficiencies ranging from 60% to 80% in field conditions and 95% under optimized settings.

Diprupa Bhaktiari (2018) from Assam has developed a simple and low-cost filter for both arsenic and iron removal using process based on oxidation-coagulation-adsorption by three common chemicals (baking soda, potassium permanganate, ferric chloride) having around 99% removal efficiency.

Abedin (2011) investigated the application of mixture of ZVI and sand to remediate the arsenic in contaminated water in a laboratory setup. The flow rate maintained for 180 days. It showed removal of 99% arsenic.

Mwakabona (2017) Usage of low-cost filters with nails as the active ZVI layer tested in field and laboratory. Fe-hydroxides to stable magnetite with incorporated As(V) achieving 60–80% As removal in fields and in lab columns >95%.

Ngai (2007) developed household water filters known as the Kanchan arsenic filter (KAF). These filters can remove 85-90% of arsenic from drinking water. The components used in these filters were sand, gravel, iron nails, brick chips and bio sand layer where iron nails can remove approximately 85–90%

Lackovic (2000) examined the use of zero-valent iron (ZVI) for the removal of inorganic arsenic from water. ZVI can reduce arsenic (III) to arsenic (V) through electron transfer. This is significant because arsenic (V) is less toxic and more readily adsorbed onto iron oxides. ZVI can achieve high arsenic removal efficiencies, often in the range of 85-99%.

OBJECTIVE:

Study and finding of arsenic content in parts of Assam and design of column tests using various filter media heights for the removal of arsenic in water and design recommendation of a low-cost filtration system based on experimental results.

METHODOLOGY:

Study Area and Sample Collection:

According to an assessment published by Assam's Public Health Engineering Department in 2023, 6881 habitations in the state are affected by arsenic across 20 districts. Baksa district in lower Assam had highest 1506 such affected habitations. In upper Assam's Jorhat district, 1454 habitations were affected followed by 1342 in Nalbari district. For this study, we had chosen and gathered water samples from seven pin points of Jorhat and Golaghat districts to find out the probable arsenic content.

Laboratory tests: Samples are tested in the laboratory of Public health Engineering Department Jorhat by standard methods for parameters such as arsenic, iron, pH, alkalinity, hardness, turbidity, conductivity, nitrate, chloride, calcium, magnesium, fluoride.

Materials Used: The following materials were selected based on local availability and prior arsenic removal research:

Iron nails: Iron oxide removes arsenic from water through a process known as adsorption, where arsenic ions bind to the surface of iron oxide particles. The arsenic ions either stick to the surface or may be incorporated into solid phases, like iron arsenate (FeAsO_4), which further reduces the arsenic's mobility in the water.

Sand: Sand may be used as a secondary or polishing layer in filters to remove any remaining fine particles or turbidity from the water after it has passed through the main arsenic-removal media and helps regulate the flow rate of water through the filter. Sand can be cleaned and reused through processes like backwashing, making it a sustainable choice for filtration.

Gravel and brick chips: Gravel serves multiple purposes, including supporting the finer filtration media, enhancing water distribution, and preventing clogging. It also aids in efficient drainage and backwashing, which helps maintain the filter's performance and longevity. brick chips play an important role in improving the filter's structure, ensuring optimal water flow, providing pre-filtration, and enhancing contact with arsenic-removal media

Bamboo charcoal: It serves as an eco-friendly and natural water purifier, harnessing its porous structure to effectively adsorb impurities and contaminants present in water. Its high surface area and absorptive qualities make it a compelling choice for water purification.

Column Design: Column tests are crucial before conducting real field tests or designing a filter system because they provide a controlled, laboratory-scale environment to simulate real-world water treatment

conditions. These tests allow for the evaluation of various filter materials, bed heights, and flow rates to determine the most effective combination for removing specific contaminants, such as arsenic or iron. Column Length 500 mm, Diameter 30mm, Material glass. Various column experiments are done using different bed height for each material and find out how it effect in removal of arsenic and other contaminants from water.

Untreated Sample Test Result

Sample No	Location	Source	Fe (Mg/L)	Arsenic (Mg/L)
1	Kaliapani, Teok	Tube Well	3.25	0.027
2	Titabar	Tube Well	1.92	0.032
3	Borhola	Tube Well	3.4	0.033
4	Dhekiakhowa, Hatigaon	Tube Well	3.49	0.020
5	Babejia Titabar	Tube Well	2.79	0.035
6	Golaghat	Tube Well	2.55	0.038
7	Central Golaghat	Tap Water	0.37	0.018

Table 1

Column Test	Components	Thickness (Cm)	Arsenic Value (Ppm)	Iron Value (Ppm)
1	Gravel	10	0.015	3.33
	Sand	10		
	Iron nails	10		
2	Gravel	10	0.025	3.18
	Sand	10		
	Unsaturated Iron nails	10		
3	Gravel	10	0.013	3.36
	Sand	15		
	Iron nail	10		
4*	Brick	5	0.026	0.78
	Sand	8		
	Charcoal	15		
	Gravel	8		
5	Gravel	10	0.010	3.30
	Sand	10		
	Charcoal	8		
	Iron nail	8		
6*	Gravel	10	0.007	3.33
	Sand	15		
	Iron nails	8		
	Brick chips	6		
7	Brick chips	6	0.010	3.29
	Sand	10		
	Charcoal	8		
	Gravel	10		
	Iron nails	10		

Table 2: Different bed height combinations for Arsenic Removal

Sl No.	Bed Height (Cm)				Arsenic Value (Ppm)	Iron Value (Ppm)	Flow Rate (L/Min)	Arsenic Removable Efficiency
	Gravel	Sand	Iron Nails	Brick Chips				
1	12	15	10	6	0.008	3.38	0.31	70.37%
2	10	10	18	10	0.010	3.57	0.25	62.96%
3	10	12	15	8	0.011	3.54	0.28	59.25%
4 *	12	18	10	6	0.004	3.39	0.18	85.18%
5	12	12	12	6	0.007	3.40	0.20	74%

Table 3: Different bed height combinations for iron removal

Sl No.	Bed Height (Cm)				Iron Value	Flow Rate	Iron Removal Efficiency
	Brick Chips	Sand	Charcoal	Gravel			
1	4	10	20	10	0.62	0.25	80.92%
2 *	4	12	22	8	0.49	0.20	94.92%
3	6	10	18	12	0.77	0.21	76.30%

Table 4: Water parameter test result using double filter experiment

Parameter	Unit	Permissible Limits	Untreated Water	Treated Water
PH		6.5-8.5	6.25	7.3
Alkalinity	mg/l	200-600	320	190
Total hardness	mg/l	200-600	344	198
Turbidity	NTU	1 -5	25	7.5
Electrical conductivity	µS/cm	Less than 1500	259	600
Nitrate	mg/l	45	3.7	3.0
Chloride	mg/l	250-1000	9.926	12.5
Calcium	mg/l	75 - 200	40	35
Magnesium	mg/l	30 - 100	73.8	39.6
Fluoride	mg/l	1 -1.5	Not detected	Not detected

Summary Of The Result And Filter Recommendation

From the seven column test results found (Table 1), column bed combination experiment no - 6 is suitable for removal of arsenic and experiment no - 4 is suitable for removal of iron from water. In Table 2 we have found out the best combination of bed heights (gravel, sand, iron nails, brick chips) and achieved 85% removal efficiency. As the iron concentration is increased due to iron nails so the suitable combinations of bed heights were found in Table 3 (using brick chips, sand, charcoal, gravel) with removal efficiency of about 94%. A double-filter system is recommended to remove arsenic concentration from water as well as to remove iron concentration. In the double-filter system, the first filter is specifically designed to target and remove arsenic from the water Second filter is introduced, which focuses on removing the excess iron, ensuring that the water meets acceptable safety standards for

both arsenic and iron content. Water quality parameters like pH, turbidity, hardness, and alkalinity and other parameters also changes and improved in the double filtration experiment. Double filtration system consistently delivers high performance and brings water quality within permissible limits.

CONCLUSION:

The study addresses the critical issue of arsenic contamination in groundwater, a serious health concern in regions like Assam, where arsenic levels often exceed the permissible limit set by the WHO. Thus, we have highlighted the viability of using iron oxide-coated bio sand filters, combined with locally available materials such as sand, bamboo charcoal, gravel, and brick chips, to achieve significant arsenic removal. This project not only offers an affordable and scalable solution to remove arsenic contamination but also contributes to the advancement of sustainable water treatment technologies. The outcomes of this

research align with the broader goals of public health improvement and environmental sustainability, making it a significant step towards addressing groundwater contamination challenges in affected areas.

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